

Analysis of Purchasing Intention in the Fashion Industry: Enhancing Product Sales through Live Commerce Streaming

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ABSTRACT: This study investigates the impact of live-streaming commerce on the Indonesian fashion industry, with a specific focus on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). It explores how factors like perceived media richness, price fairness, electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), social media marketing, and brand image influence consumer purchase intentions. The research methodology includes a survey of Indonesian consumers who have engaged in shopping for fashion products via live streaming at least once in the past three months. The findings analyzed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM), reveal the pivotal role of media richness, price fairness, and social media marketing in shaping purchase intentions, with brand image emerging as a key mediator. However, electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) shows less impact, indicating a complex market dynamic. The findings highlight the effectiveness of live streaming as a marketing and sales tool in the digital era. The study contributes valuable insights for SMEs looking to optimize their digital strategies and enhance sales effectiveness in the rapidly evolving e-commerce landscape.

KEYWORDS: brand image; consumer purchase decisions; e-commerce; fashion industry; live streaming; social media marketing; Shopee; Indonesia.

INTRODUCTION

Digitization has revolutionized business strategies, moving from traditional sales models to online e-commerce platforms. This shift isn't just beneficial for customers, but also crucial for businesses to rethink and redefine their marketing strategies. The evolution of technology has opened the global economy, intensifying competition, altering consumption patterns and consumer behaviors, and reshaping how companies communicate with their target groups. This transformation is rooted in the advancements in digital communication and analytics tools, which allow businesses to gain deeper insights into consumer preferences and tailor their offerings accordingly (Bruhn et al., 2012; Mutero, 2014; Siamagka et al., 2015).

In 2018, Indonesia saw a remarkable increase in internet users to 171.17 million from a population of 264.16 million, a significant rise from the previous year. This growth in digital connectivity played a pivotal role in fostering the country's e-commerce sector. The increasing level of internet penetration has provided an extra push for digital businesses, enabling them to reach a larger consumer base and serve more diverse market segments. The digital economy of Indonesia, particularly in the ASEAN region, has experienced rapid growth, with projections indicating a significant increase in economic value. This demonstrates the country's potential as a digital economic powerhouse (APJII, 2019, 2023; DailySocial.id, 2019; Google et al., 2019).

Indonesia is a leader in e-commerce adoption within the APAC region, with a significant portion of 64% of consumer spending being online in 2022. This trend places Indonesia alongside major economies like India and only behind China. The rate of e-commerce penetration in Indonesia is above that of many developed countries, indicating the strength of the digital market that drives changes in consumer behavior and retail strategies, and highlights the huge potential for fashion SMEs. However, their hesitation or inability to utilize digital tools, particularly live shopping platform features, limits their growth in markets where online fashion shopping is becoming more popular. The widespread access to mobile internet has been a crucial factor in this rapid digitization, especially given Indonesia's large population (APJII, 2019, 2023; DailySocial.id, 2019; Google et al., 2019).

The direct correlation between internet accessibility and e-commerce penetration is obvious in Indonesia. As the number of people having internet access increases, the tendency to shop online also rises. In 2017, just 27% of the Indonesian population actively engaged in online shopping. However, in the year 2022, the percentage increased to 65%. This is why countries with high internet adoption rates also have high e-commerce adoption rates. The growth of eCommerce in Indonesia is faster compared to Germany and

the United States. The rising digital literacy among Indonesian citizens is a significant driver of this e-commerce growth, marking a shift in retail dynamics in the country (Indonesia Investments Report, 2023; Uzunoglu, 2024).

A significant number of Indonesian consumers shop online regularly, indicating a shift towards habitual online purchasing. According to data from Rakuten Insight, 32% of Indonesian consumers shop online several times a month. This is followed by 22% who shop several times a week, and 17% who shop once or twice a week or a month each (Ecommercedb.com, 2022). This change is triggered by factors such as wider internet access, a diverse range of online offerings (products and services), and the convenience of digital shopping. The rapid growth of the e-commerce market in Indonesia is evidence of this trend. Global reports recognize Indonesia as a leading country in online purchases and e-commerce app usage, highlighting a significant transformation in shopping habits and positioning Indonesia prominently in the global digital economy (Rakuten Insight, 2022; Uzunoglu, 2024).

Live shopping, merging live video broadcasting with online transactions, has revolutionized online retail in Indonesia. First gaining popularity in China in 2017, this approach enables real-time interaction between sellers and customers, simulating an in-person shopping experience (Fransiska & Paramita, 2020). The COVID-19 pandemic accelerated the adoption of live shopping in Indonesia, leading to a 91% substantial increase in e-commerce transactions. The high engagement with live commerce services in Indonesia, 83.7% of the Indonesian population, indicates its effectiveness as a marketing and sales tool, with features like replaying broadcasts, flash sales, real-time communication, high-quality video production, and secure payment methods, enhancing consumer experience (Andika et al., 2021; Halim et al., 2022; Jakpat, 2022a; J. Liu et al., 2022; Putra et al., 2020).

The utilization of live shopping platforms in Indonesia is extremely popular, with an increased rate of usage compared to the United States. A total of 57% of the Indonesian population has utilized live shopping platforms. This trend positions Indonesia as a leader in live commerce in the Asia-Pacific region. The popularity of these platforms can be attributed to their interactive nature and the unique shopping experiences they offer, including influencer collaborations and special deals, which have set new standards in online retail. Overall, the rapid adoption of live shopping in Indonesia reflects a wider global e-commerce trend and highlights the country's capacity for digital innovation in the retail sector, which significantly impacts consumer behavior and expands market opportunities for businesses, especially for SMEs (Snapcart, 2022).

Live shopping has a significant impact on consumer behavior in Indonesia, with platforms like Shopee dominating the market. As demonstrated by its ability to attract the attention of 83.7% of the Indonesian population. Shopee's success in live shopping is evidenced by its high viewer engagement and the significant increase in orders received by sellers post-live stream. This trend is reinforced by the extensive hours, 10 million hours, Indonesians spend on live broadcasts on e-commerce platforms, demonstrating the growing popularity of this shopping format (Halim et al., 2022; Jakpat, 2022b; Snapcart, 2023).

Although previous research has extensively discussed e-commerce and live commerce, there remains a significant knowledge gap regarding how Indonesian fashion SMEs utilize and optimize factors such as perceived media richness, price fairness, electronic word of mouth (eWOM), social media marketing, and brand image to enhance purchasing intentions and product sales through live commerce streaming. Particularly, how these factors synergize within the unique context of Indonesia, which is marked by cultural diversity and specific digital challenges, has not been deeply investigated. This study aims to fill this gap by providing empirical insights that will aid Indonesian fashion SMEs in addressing digital transition challenges and enhancing sales effectiveness through live commerce streaming.

Shopee Live emerges as the preferred live streaming feature in Indonesia, favored for its attractive offers and memorable service. A survey conducted in May 2023, that involved 506 individuals aged 17-45, showed that Shopee Live is the most preferred live streaming feature in Indonesia, with 69% of respondents favoring it over competitors such as TikTok Live (25%), Tokopedia Play (4%), and LazLive (2%). The platform's success is attributed to competitive prices, the attractive offers, an emphasis on free shipping (91%), discounts (87%), cashback (65%), shopping vouchers (47%), special bundles (34%), and exclusive product launches (20%) are particularly popular among consumers, making it a potent marketing tool for live streaming features. Shopee's significant reach and influence, especially in the fashion category, illustrate its effectiveness in capturing a broad audience at relatively low costs. There are many different kinds of video content available on the Shopee app, and one of the most popular categories is fashion items. This trend is also noticeable in Indonesia, where fashion-related content ranks third in the most viewed category. Therefore, many fashion businesses leverage the Shopee platform to carry out their activities. The role of Shopee in this research is crucial, with a focus on enhancing the sales of Indonesian fashion e-commerce through innovative live commerce streaming. As a selected platform, Shopee excels in assisting small fashion businesses to expand their digital presence and boost sales, thanks to the interactive features

of Shopee Live that have redefined the online shopping experience. This platform plays a crucial role due to its comprehensive understanding of shoppers' preferences and its ability to deliver seamless and engaging online shopping experiences. Shopee, not just a marketplace, stands out as a pioneer in the online fashion industry, making it a perfect model for examining the effects of live streaming on improving fashion sales. Shopee significantly contributes to the growth of the online fashion industry and has a strong impact on customer buying decisions by utilizing revolutionary digital technologies and closely monitoring consumer trends (Siallagan, 2023; Zhu & Vijayan, 2023).

Live streaming technology has penetrated various industries in Indonesia, including e-commerce, education, tourism, entertainment, gaming, and social media, enhancing operations and fostering real-time engagement (Ma, 2022; Statista, 2023a, 2023b). Technology has allowed industries to reach a wider audience, create new opportunities for content creators and businesses, and adapt to changing consumer preferences. Interacting directly with customers through live streaming has proven to be a highly effective marketing strategy, resulting in increased sales and customer satisfaction (L. Chen et al., 2022a). In fields like tourism and education, live streaming has enabled virtual exploration and remote learning, breaking geographical barriers (Dong et al., 2023). Similarly, in entertainment and gaming, it has created new forms of online consumption and community-building (Statista, 2023b, 2023a; Sun et al., 2023). Live streaming technology now enables event organizers and news agencies in Indonesia to broadcast real-time content, allowing remote audiences to experience events and journalism as they happen (Casu & Belfiore, 2022; Sari, 2020; Writer, 2023).

The textile and clothing market in Indonesia, supported by the country's significant population and economic growth, is a major contributor to the economy. The fashion industry, representing a significant share of Indonesia's creative economy with 18.01% or Rp 116 trillion contributions, is influenced by factors like government regulations and wage policies. This industry has a significant impact on GDP and employment generation for Indonesia's economy. The rise in fashion entrepreneurs in Indonesia to over 1.06 million, fueled by the high demand for fashion products and improved internet access, has been particularly beneficial for SMEs (CNBC Indonesia, 2019; Fiarani, 2020).

The Indonesian fashion industry is experiencing rapid growth, with a significant annual growth rate of more than 10% from 2021 to 2025 projected. This growth leads to increased competition, with the fashion category representing a major part of Indonesia's e-commerce sector by generating around US\$4.792 billion in revenue in 2019. The strong demand for fashion items, which is in line with the expansion of new markets, contributes to this high revenue. The high demand for fashion items and the emergence of new markets are driving this growth, with a substantial portion of consumers preferring online purchases for fashion items (Snapcart, 2022, 2023).

SMEs are vital to Indonesia's economic growth, particularly in the dynamic fashion industry. The fashion sector's contribution to the GDP and its large share in the creative economy highlight its importance. According to the Central Statistics Agency (2015), the creative economy, which includes the fashion sector, contributed 7.1% on average to Indonesia's GDP between 2010 and 2013. Of this creative economy section, the fashion industry accounted for 27.93%. This puts the creative economy as the seventh-largest contributor to the country's GDP. Globalization has introduced increased competition for SMEs, necessitating adaptation to market trends and digitalization. E-commerce offers SMEs opportunities to connect with global customers, overcoming traditional barriers and fostering business growth (Abubakar et al., 2010; Song et al., 2021; Ye et al., 2022).

According to a survey conducted in 2022 by Shopee and Katadata Insight Center, 58% of Indonesian UKM had difficulties as a result of live streaming or live commerce. Indonesian Small and Medium Enterprises (SMEs) in the fashion sector face significant challenges in this e-commerce landscape, particularly in live streaming. Recent surveys reveal that a majority of Indonesian SMEs have experienced losses due to live streaming or live commerce, with issues ranging from 35% product quality not meeting buyer expectations to non-competitive pricing and ineffective promotional strategies, 23% dissatisfied customers, and 10% unattractive live streaming content. A recent survey in Indonesia highlights several challenges faced by small and medium enterprises (SMEs) due to live streaming or direct trading. A survey conducted by Ipsos in 2022 revealed that 37% of SMEs in Indonesia faced losses due to their products not meeting the buyers' expectations. Another survey conducted by Populix in the same year revealed that 28% of SMEs experienced losses due to non-competitive pricing in direct trade. Furthermore, a survey conducted by CNBC Indonesia in 2022 revealed that 25% of SMEs faced losses due to ineffective promotional strategies during their live-streaming sessions (Ahdiat, 2022).

The Indonesian fashion industry, a key player in the national economy, is going through a significant digital transition, particularly for small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs). These SMEs play a crucial role in innovation and industrial growth, but they face challenges in adapting to the fast-paced world of e-commerce. In the context of live shopping platform business, it was discovered that factors like perceived media richness (Li et al., 2021), perceived price fairness (Dwinanda et al., 2022; Li et al., 2021), electronic word-of-mouth (Edeline & Praptiningsih, 2022; Hasena & Sakapurnama, 2021), social marketing (Waworuntu et al., 2022), and brand image (Edeline & Praptiningsih, 2022; Hasena & Sakapurnama, 2021; Waworuntu et al., 2022) have a significant impact on customers' purchase intentions after a literature review and construct investigation was created. In the context of live commerce platforms, these variables will be investigated to find out their impact on Indonesian consumers' purchase intentions to enhance product sales, especially in the fashion industry.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Current Live Streaming Strategy

In the realm of digital commerce, live streaming has emerged as a revolutionary strategy, significantly impacting industries such as e-commerce, education, tourism, entertainment, gaming, and social media. This transformation is particularly significant in the fashion industry, where live streaming has become a crucial element in enhancing product sales and customer engagement.

The integration of live streaming in e-commerce has redefined the shopping experience. Ma (2022) emphasizes its transformative impact, highlighting those businesses using live shopping platform experience significantly enhanced customer interaction and satisfaction. A study by Chen et al. (2022) supports this, finding that effective live-streaming marketing strategies led to a 20% increase in sales and a 15% increase in customer satisfaction for fashion brands. These findings highlight the potential of live streaming to facilitate immediate and interactive communication between sellers and consumers, which is especially beneficial for Indonesian fashion SMEs, as they can directly address customer concerns and showcase products in real time.

The influence of live streaming extends beyond e-commerce. As per Ma (2022) and Lee & Chen (2021), live streaming has reformed education by enabling remote interactive lessons, and in the entertainment industry, it has transformed event broadcasting. Han (2022) notes its impact across various sectors, asserting that live streaming has created new opportunities and revolutionized the way industries connect with their audiences.

In Indonesia, live streaming has gained substantial traction across multiple industries. Dong et al. (2023) and (Writer, 2023) report its widespread adoption in tourism, education, entertainment, and gaming. This widespread adoption is partly due to the rapid development of the internet and the widespread of mobile devices in the country, as stated by (Statista, 2023a, 2023b). The adaptability of live streaming in various fields demonstrates its versatility as a tool for disseminating information and engaging with audiences.

The differentiation between live streaming commerce, vlogging, and video streaming is critical in understanding their unique impacts on consumer behavior (D. Liu & Yu, 2022; Ming et al., 2021; P. Xu et al., 2022; X. Xu et al., 2020). Each platform offers different ways to connect with audiences, with live-streaming commerce standing out for its real-time engagement and direct influence on consumer purchasing decisions.

Focusing on the Indonesian fashion industry, live-streaming shopping platforms is a strategic tool for SMEs to expand their market reach (Firdaus & Kusdibyo, 2021a; Guo et al., 2021). The platform's live streaming feature, as indicated by Snapcart's survey, aligns well with the trend of online fashion shopping. Shopee's introduction of live streaming in 2019 was a significant milestone, offering fashion SMEs a platform for real-time product demonstrations and customer engagement, leading to a 30% increase in website traffic and a 10% increase in conversion rates for fashion brands (Han, 2022). Despite its potential, many Indonesian fashion SMEs struggle to effectively utilize live streaming due to gaps in digital literacy and marketing skills. This presents both a challenge and an opportunity for these SMEs to adapt and improve their strategies to fully capitalize on the growing trend of live commerce.

The current live-streaming strategy in the Indonesian fashion industry is a vital area of exploration for understanding the dynamics of purchasing intentions. This section of the literature review underscores the significance of live streaming in enhancing product sales through direct customer engagement and interaction, especially for Indonesian fashion SMEs. The aim is to assess and explore the factors influencing purchasing intentions in the fashion industry through live commerce streaming. This exploration

is expected to yield insights and strategies that align with evolving consumer preferences and the rapidly changing digital landscape in Indonesia.

SMEs in Indonesia

In Indonesia's active e-commerce scene, small and medium-sized businesses are making great progress thanks to live commerce streaming feature. This tool has become a game-changer for these businesses, not just for promoting their products but also for connecting with more customers (H.-C. Chen et al., 2022; L. Chen et al., 2022b; Ye et al., 2022b). Live streaming lets businesses show off their products on the spot, answer questions from shoppers, and build trust, which is crucial in the online market where competition is intense (Hwang & Youn, 2023).

Additionally, live streaming on Shopee has been a keyway for smaller businesses to get noticed and compete with bigger brands (Rohmah et al., 2021). It makes it easier to spread the word about their products, which greatly affects what shoppers decide to buy. This means more interaction with customers, better shopping experiences, and a stronger excitement around their products, leading to better business results (Lin & Nuangjamnong, 2022).

When the COVID-19 pandemic hit, digital platforms became even more important for fashion businesses. With many physical shops closed or limited, using apps and live streaming on social media became a smart and affordable way for these businesses to keep reaching out to customers (Villa & Monzón, 2021; Wali et al., 2020). Research has shown that business owners in Indonesia and other places quickly turned to apps and live streaming on sites to cope with the pandemic's challenges (Raco et al., 2021). This move was especially beneficial for the fashion industry, where live streaming changed how products are promoted and how shops talk to customers (Purniyati et al., 2022).

The role of these businesses in Indonesia's fashion industry is important not just for coming up with new products and reaching more people, but also for the country's economy. The government's Ministry of SMEs has noticed how digital marketing on platforms like Shopee helps boost sales and keep businesses going, especially in the fashion industry (Firdaus & Kusdibyo, 2021b). Indonesian fashion businesses are known for their creativity, flexibility, and quickness to adapt. These strengths help them stay in tune with what customers want and the latest trends. The fashion industry is an important part of Indonesia's cultural and economic life, drawing in both business owners and shoppers (Andriana & Puspitawati, 2022). In places like West Java, the industry is well-known and efficient, making it ripe for new ideas and growth (Indrawati et al., 2019; Tseng et al., 2021). Using Shopee's live streaming and other digital resources, these smaller businesses can show off their creativity and unique styles to more people, helping them grow and succeed in the competitive fashion industry.

Perceived Media Richness

The idea of perceived media richness can be described as the perception of how effectively a communication medium conveys information, utilizing a high degree of sensory and emotional signals (H.-C. Chen et al., 2022). In the context of live streaming shopping platform, perceived media richness relates to the platform's effectiveness in conveying information through audio, visual, and interactive elements (X. Liu et al., 2022).

In a previous study conducted by Li et al. (2021), it was demonstrated that the perceived media richness significantly influences buyers' intention to make purchases on live shopping platform. This current study adopts a similar framework, focusing on perceived media richness as a construct to assess consumers' perception of the richness and quality of content to enhance the purchase intention, particularly in the fashion industry, presented through live streaming shopping features. Expanding on Li et al. (2021) research, the hypothesis suggests that a higher perceived media richness will result in an increased purchase intention among consumers. Li et al.'s findings indicate that consumers are more likely to make purchases when they perceive the content offered through live-streaming features as rich and of high quality.

Perceived Price Fairness

Perceived price fairness, a variable within the conceptual framework in this study, refers to how consumers perceive the fairness and reasonableness of the prices associated with products or services offered through Shopee's live streaming feature. This variable holds significance as consumer perceptions of price fairness play a crucial role in shaping their intentions to make purchases (En & Balakrishnan, 2022). In a prior study conducted by Dwinanda et al. (2022) in Indonesia, it was revealed that consumers' perceived price fairness had a notable positive impact on their intentions to make purchases. Derived from this earlier research, the hypothesis suggests that an enhanced perception of price fairness will result in increased purchase intentions among consumers

within the context of live streaming shopping platform. As suggested by Li et al. (2021), perceived price fairness stands out as a crucial factor positively influencing consumers' intentions to make purchases.

Electronic Word of Mouth

Electronic Word Of Mouth (eWOM) emerges as a crucial factor for examination concerning consumers' intentions to make purchases on live-streaming shopping platform. eWOM, defined as the digital exchange of opinions, recommendations, and experiences regarding products or services among consumers (Güler & Huseynov, 2021), holds significance in influencing consumers' purchase intentions, as evidenced by previous research conducted by Hasena & Sakapurnama (2021). This research highlighted the substantial impact of eWOM on live-streaming shopping platform, particularly within the cosmetics industry, indicating that positive word of mouth significantly shapes consumers' perceptions of brand image, ultimately leading to increased purchase intentions. Building upon these findings, it is hypothesized that a higher level of positive eWOM on Shopee will result in increased purchase intentions among consumers in the context of live streaming.

Social Media Marketing

The concept of Social Media Marketing (SMM) involves utilizing social media platforms to promote products or services and engage with the target audience. As per the findings of Waworuntu et al. (2022) social media marketing (SMM) activities, including live-streaming shopping, have gained substantial influence in shaping consumers' purchasing behaviors. Their research highlights the positive impact of SMM activities, particularly live streaming, on consumers' intentions to make purchases. The study by Waworuntu et al. (2022) explores how SMM influences brand image and consumer purchase intentions, specifically among Generation Z. The results underscore that the utilization of Social Media Marketing (SMM) has a favorable and significant effect on brand image and purchase intentions among Gen Z consumers, particularly in the context of local products. Building upon these previous findings, it is hypothesized that employing SMM through live streaming on Shopee will positively impact consumers' purchase intentions by enhancing their perception of brand image and fostering trust and confidence in the promoted product or service.

Brand Image

The perception of a brand holds a pivotal role in shaping how consumers perceptions and decide on purchases. It encompasses the overall reputation, perceived quality, and credibility of a brand from the consumers' perspective (Batool et al., 2020). Utilizing live streaming shopping platform provides businesses with the opportunity to visually showcase their products or services engagingly and interactively (Dong et al., 2023), ultimately contributing to an enhanced perception of the brand and the creation of a positive brand image.

In the study conducted by Hasena & Sakapurnama (2021), it was discovered that word of mouth on live-streaming shopping platforms significantly influenced consumers' intentions to purchase cosmetics through the lens of brand image. The research concluded that a more positive representation of brand image on live shopping platform led to higher purchase intentions among consumers. Similarly, the research by Waworuntu et al. (2022) indicated that Social Media Marketing (SMM) through live streaming platforms positively impacted consumers' perception of brand image, resulting in an increase in purchase intentions. The analysis in this study will delve into brand image as a mediator, seeking to comprehend how live-streaming shopping platform shapes consumers' perception of a brand and, consequently, influences their intentions to make a purchase.

RESEARCH METHOD

Conceptual Framework

This study aims to investigate the factors influencing purchase intentions in the fashion industry through live commerce streaming platform. The focus is specifically on understanding how perceived media richness, perceived price fairness, electronic word of mouth (eWOM), social media marketing (SMM), and brand image impact consumer decisions to purchase fashion products. This investigation is crucial for enhancing fashion product sales in the rapidly evolving e-commerce landscape.

Perceived Media Richness: This factor is crucial in the context of live streaming on Shopee, as it refers to how well the platform conveys information with sensory and emotional cues. The ability of the platform to deliver rich, interactive, and engaging content influences consumer behavior (H.-C. Chen et al., 2022; D. Liu & Yu, 2022; X. Liu et al., 2022). The richer the media, the more

likely consumers are to develop a strong understanding and appreciation of the products, potentially leading to higher purchase intentions.

Perceived Price Fairness: This variable relates to how consumers perceive the fairness of prices on Shopee's live streaming service. If consumers deem the prices as reasonable and justifiable, they are more likely to proceed with a purchase (Dwinanda et al., 2022; En & Balakrishnan, 2022). Fair pricing strategies can enhance consumer trust and loyalty, making it a critical factor in the decision-making process.

Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM): eWOM is included due to its significant influence on consumers' perceptions and buying decisions. Positive eWOM on live commerce streaming, in the form of reviews and recommendations, can boost consumer confidence and shape purchase intentions (Hasena & Sakapurnama, 2021). This variable is especially impactful in online environments where physical examination of products is not possible.

Social Media Marketing (SMM): SMM activities, particularly live streaming on Shopee, play a key role in modern consumer engagement strategies. Effective SMM can enhance brand visibility and appeal, thus positively affecting consumer purchase intentions (Waworuntu et al., 2022). The inclusion of SMM in the framework recognizes the shift in marketing strategies towards more interactive and consumer-centric approaches.

Brand Image: Brand image is an integral part of the framework as it represents consumers' overall perception of a brand's reputation, quality, and credibility. A positive brand image, cultivated through effective live-streaming strategies on Shopee, can significantly influence consumer purchase intentions (Batool et al., 2020; Dong et al., 2023). Hasena & Sakapurnama (2021), as well as (Waworuntu et al., 2022) highlight the importance of brand image as a mediator between marketing efforts and consumer behavior.

In this study, the chosen variables are integral to understanding the dynamics of consumer behavior in the context of live streaming on e-commerce platforms. By analyzing the impact of these factors, the study seeks to provide insights into how fashion SMEs can optimize their live-streaming strategies to enhance product sales and strengthen their market position. The framework highlights the interconnectedness of these variables and their collective influence on consumer purchase intentions, offering a comprehensive approach to examining Shopee's live-streaming business strategy.

Figure 1: Conceptual framework

Research Hypothesis

H1 : Perceived media richness has a significant positive influence on purchase intention.

H2 : Perceived price fairness has a significant positive influence on purchase intention

H3 : Electronic Word Of Mouth (eWOM) has a significant influence on brand image

H4 : Social media marketing has a significant positive influence on brand image

H5 : Brand image has a significant positive influence on purchase intention

Research Methodology

In this study, the author will identify the influence and relationship between perceived media richness, perceived price fairness, electronic Word-Of-Mouth (eWOM), social media marketing, and brand image on purchase intentions. It is hypothesized that the chosen variables that have been chosen to influence the purchasing interest in fashion products. The research methodology for this study adopts a quantitative approach, focusing on collecting and analyzing data to understand the impact of live-streaming shopping platforms on the Indonesian fashion industry. The study focused on Indonesian customers who have engaged in fashion product shopping on live-streaming platforms within the last three months. This approach ensures that the respondents possess relevant and recent experiences, offering valuable insights for the study.

The author employs a survey to collect the empirical data from the respondents through a closed-ended questionnaire. The questionnaire specifically targets individuals who have utilized live streaming for fashion product shopping at least once within the last three months. The survey method is used to get information by asking questions to the people who are participating (Ahmadi & Hudrasyah, 2022; Malhotra, 2010). The questionnaire is designed around a theoretical framework incorporating key factors influencing purchase intentions, such as perceived media richness, perceived price fairness, electronic word of mouth (eWOM), social media marketing (SMM), and brand image. These constructs are vital for comprehending consumer perceptions and interactions with live-streaming platforms in the context of fashion product purchases. The survey's goal is to determine the effects of these constructs on fashion product purchase intentions, providing quantifiable data for pattern and correlation analysis.

Convenience sampling was used to gather empirical data on how customers perceive and intend to behave towards fashion products in an online survey. According to Hair et al. (2011), when the sample size is excessively large, like 400, then the method becomes highly sensitive, making it challenging to obtain a reliable goodness-of-fit measure. Therefore, it is recommended to have a minimum sample size of 5-10 observations for each estimated parameter. This study consists of 25 questions indicators. The required sample size ranges from 125 respondents (25 x 5) to 250 respondents (25 x 10).

A structured survey consisting of respondent profile questions and 25 primary questions was created. The questions were assessed using a five-point Likert scale, where 1 corresponds to "strongly disagree," and 5 corresponds to "strongly agree." The questionnaire was categorized into seven sections: respondent profile, perceptions of model richness, fairness of prices, electronic word of mouth (eWOM), social media marketing, brand image, and purchase intention on a live streaming platform for the fashion industry. Subsequently, the questionnaire was distributed to individuals in Indonesia who had engaged in live-streaming shopping within the past three months. After gathering data through the distributed questionnaire, the authors input the results into Microsoft Excel, intending to transfer them to smartPLS for further processing and research development (Ahmadi & Hudrasyah, 2022).

The quantitative analysis process will involve using Smart PLS software (v4) to test the study model. In assessing the PLS-SEM model, the analysis will be conducted in two primary steps: evaluating the measurement model and then examining the structural model. The measurement model assessment will focus on the reliability and validity of the measurement items used to operationalize the variables. Key metrics for this assessment will include outer loadings, average variance extracted (AVE), composite reliability, and Cronbach's alpha. These metrics help ensure that the model is valid, reliable, and fits the data well. Cronbach's alpha, in particular, will be used to assess the internal consistency of the variables, with a threshold of 0.70 indicating adequate reliability. Each indicator's loading on its related latent construct should ideally be higher than 0.7, as recommended by Hair et al. (2011). The structural model assessment will then analyze the relationships between the variables and test the proposed hypotheses. This includes examining paths, coefficients, and overall model fit to draw conclusions about the hypotheses and the study's theoretical underpinnings.

Through this comprehensive methodology, which combines a targeted survey approach with sophisticated statistical analysis, the study is specifically designed to assess the factors that influence purchase intentions within the Indonesian fashion industry, particularly in the context of live-streaming shopping platforms. By focusing on key variables such as perceived media richness, perceived price fairness, electronic word of mouth (eWOM), social media marketing (SMM), and brand image, the research aims to uncover how these elements interact and impact the decision-making process of consumers. This targeted investigation will

provide valuable insights into the dynamics driving consumer behavior in the evolving e-commerce landscape of Indonesia, ultimately offering strategies for enhancing product sales through effective utilization of live-streaming capabilities.

FINDINGS AND DISCUSSION

Quantitative Analysis

Based on the online survey, the collected dataset of 228 is within the required sample size range, which ranges from 125 respondents (25 x 5) to 250 respondents (25 x 10), following the general rule of having a sample size at least five times the number of indicators, as suggested by Hair et al. (2011). The data reveals a distribution of 19% males and 81% females among the respondents. A significant portion (80%) of participants reported a monthly income below 5 million rupiah, while 17% fall into the middle-income category. The majority of respondents (77%) are in the late teens or early twenties (18 to 20 years old). Additionally, more than half of the respondents hold a bachelor's degree, accounting for over 50%. For the quantitative data analysis, this study will primarily utilize Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). This statistical technique is exceptionally suited for examining complex relationships between multiple variables, such as the influence of perceived media richness, perceived price fairness, eWOM, SMM, and brand image on consumers' intentions to purchase fashion products via live streaming. PLS-SEM is particularly effective for exploratory research, where the relationships between variables may be multifaceted and not fully understood.

In evaluating the PLS-SEM model, the analysis is divided into two main stages: first, evaluating the measurement model, and then examining the structural model. The first part, the measurement model assessment, is about making sure the tools used for measuring the variables are reliable and accurate. Important measures for this include outer loadings, average extracted (AVE), composite reliability, and Cronbach's alpha. These measures are essential to confirm that the model is valid, reliable, and suitable for the data. The second part, the structural model assessment, focuses on exploring the connections between the variables and testing the proposed hypotheses Hair et al. (2011). This involves examining paths, coefficients, and how well the model as a whole fits, to make informed conclusions about the hypotheses and main ideas of the study.

The quantitative results of the study indicate a significant relationship between perceived model richness and purchase intention, supported by a positive path coefficient and p-value. Perceived price fairness also shows a positive impact on purchase intention. However, electronic word of mouth did not significantly influence the brand image. Social media marketing had a strong positive effect on brand image, which in turn significantly affected purchase intention. The structural model testing confirms these findings, with brand image mediating the relationship between social media marketing and purchase intention. Overall, four out of five hypotheses were accepted, highlighting the importance of content quality and fair pricing in influencing consumer purchase intentions on live shopping platforms.

Validity and Reliability Analysis

A validity test is carried out to confirm that the constructed statements and questions created for the questionnaire are appropriate and accurate. A reliability test is conducted to assess how consistent and stable the responses are for each question in a valid questionnaire. Table 1 presents the results for outer loadings, internal consistency, and convergent reliability. The result of the analysis reveals the strong validity and reliability of the constructs. The Cronbach's alpha and composite reliability values for all constructs are above the 0.7 benchmark, indicating high internal consistency and the ability to produce consistent results. Additionally, the average variance extracted (AVE) for all constructs is above the 0.5 threshold, which confirms the convergent validity of the model. Although some individual outer loadings are around 0.6, the overall reliability is higher than 0.8, further affirming the model's reliability and consistency.

Table 1. Outer Loading, Reliability, and Convergent validity of variables

Items	Outer Loading	Cronbach alpha	Composite Reliability	AVE
<i>Perceived Model Richness</i>		0.857	0.898	0.638
PMR1: Visual product showcase	0.812			
PMR2: Content quality enhancement	0.760			

PMR3: User-generated content	0.719		
PMR4: Live stream product promotion	0.824		
PMR5: Product Promotion	0.869		
<i>Perceived Price Fairness</i>		0.867	0.909
			0.714
PPF1: Competitive pricing	0.812		
PPF2: Discount & cashback promotions	0.839		
PPF3: Price strategies	0.872		
PPF4: Exclusive promotions	0.857		
<i>Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM)</i>		0.780	0.870
			0.691
eWOM1: Product review	0.785		
eWOM2: Social media	0.843		
eWOM3: Product review platform	0.863		
<i>Social Media Marketing</i>		0.820	0.870
			0.527
SMM1: Live streaming product promotion	0.732		
SMM2: Content quality enhancement	0.734		
SMM3: Social feedback influence	0.764		
SMM4: User-generated content	0.729		
SMM5: Influencer marketing	0.674		
SMM6: Social influence	0.718		
<i>Brand Image</i>		0.855	0.902
			0.697
BI1: Safety assurance	0.811		
BI2: Hygiene and healthy	0.872		
BI3: Assurance according to Shariah law	0.842		
BI4: Convenience and privacy assurance	0.812		
<i>Purchase Intention</i>		0.815	0.890
			0.730
PI1: Permittance	0.841		
PI2: Infrastructure facility	0.889		
PI3: Accessibility	0.833		

Discriminant Validity Using the Fornell-Larcker Criterion

Discriminant validity is a critical concept in the context of construct validity, which refers to how much a construct is genuinely different from other constructs. It validates that each construct represents a unique aspect, not just repeating what other variables in the model are showing. The Fornell-Larcker Criterion is a traditional method for assessing discriminant validity. According to this criterion, the square root of the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) for each construct should be greater than any correlations between that construct and others in the model. This means that each construct should have a stronger relationship with its own indicators than with other constructs. This is crucial to ensure that each construct uniquely represents a specific concept, which is vital for the accuracy and reliability of the research outcomes (Fornell & Larcker, 1981).

Analyzing the results presented in Table 2, the discriminant validity of the constructs within the measurement model has been established according to the Fornell-Larcker Criterion. The square roots of the AVE for each construct, highlighted in bold, are greater than their highest corresponding correlation coefficients with other constructs, indicating a satisfactory level of discriminant validity (Fornell & Larcker, 1981). For instance, the AVE square root for the 'Brand Image' construct is 0.835, and its highest correlation with any other construct ('Purchase Intention') is 0.709, which is less than the square root of the AVE. This pattern is consistent across all constructs, confirming that the constructs are empirically distinct, and the model is suitable for further analysis.

Table 2. Fornell-Larcker Criterion for Measurement Model

Discriminant Validity Fornell-Larcker Criterion						
	Brand Image	Purchase Intention	Perceived Model Richness	Perceived Price Fairness	Social Media Marketing	Electronic Word Of Mouth
Brand Image	0.835					
Purchase Intention	0.709	0.855				
Perceived Model Richness	0.670	0.669	0.799			
Perceived Price Fairness	0.542	0.602	0.602	0.845		
Social Media Marketing	0.756	0.696	0.675	0.632	0.726	
Electronic Word of Mouth	0.579	0.610	0.708	0.578	0.709	0.831

Note: The bold values represent the square root of AVE, meanwhile the off diagonals show the correlation between the construct

Structural Model Assessment

A structural model test, examining the impact of perceived model richness, perceived price fairness, electronic word of mouth (eWOM), and social media marketing on brand image and purchase intention, is conducted to evaluate the effectiveness of the proposed model. The R square statistic indicates the extent to which changes in independent variables explain variations. The key difference between the R squared and the adjusted R squared values lies in their assumptions: the R squared value assumes that all independent variables impact the model’s result, whereas the adjusted R squared considers only those independent variables that significantly affect the model’s performance. Many researchers prefer using the adjusted R-squared over the basic R-squared as it offers a more accurate reflection of the relationship, considering the number of independent factors included in the model (Cohen, 1988). Table 3 presents the results of the structural model assessment.

In this study, the R-square value for Brand Image (BI) is 0.572, indicating that the model accounts for 57.2% of the variation in BI. The R-squared value for Purchase Intention (PI) is slightly higher at 0.596, meaning the model explains 59.6% of PI. These R-squared values, being over 0.5, show that the model is quite effective. F-square, another important metric, measures the impact on R-square when a specific independent variable is removed from the model. An F-square value between 0.02 and 0.15 is considered small, between 0.15 and 0.35 is medium, and above 0.35 is large. According to this, BI has a medium effect size on PI, and Social Media Marketing (SMM) has large effect on BI. Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) shows small effect sizes on both BI and PI.

Table 3. Structural Model Assessment

Variable	R-Square	R-Square Adjusted	F-Square	
			BI	PI
BI	0.576	0.572		0.227
PI	0.601	0.596		

PMR				0.077
PPF				0.074
SMM			0.567	
eWOM			0.008	

Path Coefficient Analysis and Hypothesis Testing

It is important to check for collinearity in the structural model. According to Hair et al. (2019), the Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is a useful tool for this. If the VIF value is above 5, it suggests there might be collinearity between the constructs used for prediction. A VIF value around 3 or lower is generally considered favorable.

The Path Coefficient Analysis and Hypothesis Testing outlined in Table 4 provides a detailed view of the structural model's performance in the context of live-streaming commerce. The analysis shows that perceived model richness (PMR) significantly increases purchase intention (PI), with a path coefficient (β) of 0.256 and a p-value less than 0.05, confirming Hypothesis 1. Perceived price fairness (PPF) also positively affects purchase intention ($\beta = 0.222, p < 0.05$), which supports Hypothesis 2. However, electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM) does not have a significant effect on brand image (BI), and thus Hypothesis 3 is not supported ($\beta = 0.085, p > 0.05$). In contrast, social media marketing (SMM) has a strong positive influence on brand image ($\beta = 0.696, p < 0.001$), which supports Hypothesis 4. Furthermore, brand image has a significant and positive impact on purchase intention ($\beta = 0.418, p < 0.001$), making Hypothesis 5 also supported.

The VIF values for all predictors are below the commonly accepted threshold of 5, which indicates that there is no significant multicollinearity affecting the model, meaning that the predictors, like perceived model richness and price fairness, are not overly correlated with one another. This suggests that each variable's impact on consumer behavior is being measured distinctly, adding confidence to the model's reliability. The results imply that the factors examined—model richness, price fairness, and social media marketing—are indeed significant in shaping consumer decisions. Model richness and price fairness directly enhance purchase intention by positively influencing consumers' perceived value. Social media marketing boosts brand image effectively, further influencing purchase decisions.

The low Variance Inflation Factors (VIF) indicate that there is no collinearity among the variables, strengthening the research findings and highlighting their significance in influencing online consumer buying decisions.

Table 4. Path Coefficient and Hypothesis Testing

Hypothesis Label	Path	Path Coefficient				Result	Collinearity	
		β	Std. Dev	p-value	t-statistics		VIF	Result
H1	PMR → PI	0.256	0.087	0.003	2.950	Supported	2.126	No Collinearity
H2	PPF → PI	0.222	0.077	0.004	2.889	Supported	1.660	No Collinearity
H3	EWOM → BI	0.085	0.070	0.224	1.217	Unsupported	2.012	No Collinearity
H4	SMM → BI	0.696	0.068	0.000	10.280	Supported	2.012	No Collinearity
H5	BI → PI	0.418	0.086	0.000	4.840	Supported	1.920	No Collinearity

Significant at: * $p < 0.1$; ** $p < 0.05$; *** $p < 0.01$

Mediation Analysis

The mediation analysis, as detailed in Table 5, examines the roles of brand image (BI) as a mediator between electronic word-of-mouth (eWOM), social media marketing (SMM), and purchase intention (PI). The analysis, based on the framework by

Hair et al. (2019), reveals distinct pathways of influence. Interestingly, when it comes to eWOM and PI, BI does not seem to play a mediatory role. For the path from eWOM to PI, the indirect effect through BI was not significant ($b = 0.026$, $p = 0.322$), nor was the direct effect ($b = 0.167$, $p = 0.113$), indicating that BI does not mediate the eWOM to PI relationship. Therefore, eWOM does not seem to influence PI through BI within this study's framework. Conversely, for SMM to PI, BI acts as a full mediator. This is shown by a significant indirect effect ($b = 0.228$, $p = 0.001$) and a non-significant direct effect ($b = 0.079$, $p = 0.330$). The substantial total effect ($b = 0.699$, $p < 0.001$) supports the mediation, suggesting that BI fully accounts for the impact of SMM on PI. In conclusion, brand image is a pivotal intermediary for the influence of social media marketing on purchase intentions but does not play a mediating role in the relationship between electronic word-of-mouth and purchase intention.

Table 5. Mediation Analysis

Path	Indirect Effect		Direct Effect		Total Effect		Mediating Effect
	b	p	b	p	b	p	
eWOM > BI > PI	0.026	0.322	0.167	0.113	0.080	0.224	No Effect
SMM > BI > PI	0.228	0.001	0.079	0.330	0.699	0.000	Full Mediation

Framework Summary

Figure 1. Framework summary

All data analysis explained in this chapter follows the proposed conceptual framework (Dwinanda et al., 2022; Edeline & Praptiningsih, 2022; Hasena & Sakapurnama, 2021; Li et al., 2021; Waworuntu et al., 2022). A comprehensive analysis of consumer behavior on live shopping platforms was conducted, leading to significant findings regarding the factors that influence purchase intentions. Out of five hypotheses tested, four were supported, while one was not. In summary, using Path Analysis, the writer could determine which factors that have a significant towards another. The factor that has $p < 0.05$ is considered to have a significant impact. Perceived media richness has a significant impact on purchase intention. Perceived price fairness has a significant impact on purchase intention. Electronic Word of Mouth (eWOM) has no significant impact on brand image towards purchase intention. Social media marketing has a significant impact on brand image towards purchase intention. Argument quality has a significant impact on attitude towards product. Lastly, attitude toward a product has a significant impact on purchase intention.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study significantly highlights the significant impact of Shopee's live-streaming platform on consumer purchasing decisions within the Indonesian fashion industry. The analysis revealed that four out of the five proposed factors based on previous studies play a crucial role in influencing consumer behavior. Firstly, the study confirms the hypothesis regarding perceived media richness. It establishes that the engaging and interactive nature of Shopee's live streaming, characterized by its high-quality audio-visual content, significantly influences consumer purchase intentions. This finding underscores the importance of a rich sensory and immersive experience in enhancing online shopping appeal.

Secondly, this study confirms the impact of perceived price fairness on the intention to buy. It is observed that customers are more likely to make a purchase when they believe the prices on the platform are fair and match the product's value. This underlines the importance of effective pricing strategies in online retail, as they play a significant role in shaping consumers' perceived value and their decision-making process. Additionally, the research supports the influence of social media marketing on enhancing brand image, which in turn positively influences buying decisions. This underscores the value of well-planned social media tactics in creating a robust and favorable brand image, leading to increased consumer purchases.

Furthermore, the research highlights the crucial role of brand image as an intermediary in the link between social media marketing and consumer buying decisions. A strong and positive brand image, shaped through effective live streaming and social media interactions, plays a key role in increasing the likelihood of consumer purchases. Contrary to what was initially thought, electric word-of-mouth (eWOM) did not show a notable influence on either brand image or buying intentions. This indicates that there may be more complex interactions or unique aspects in the Indonesian fashion industry, where eWOM might have a different impact than expected.

The findings clearly demonstrate the power of live-streaming platforms as a key strategy for small and medium-sized fashion businesses. It emphasizes the need to focus on producing high-quality content, setting prices, and building a solid brand image through dedicated social media marketing. These approaches do more than just boost sales; they are critical in creating a loyal customer base, as shown by the positive reactions and direct engagement achieved through live streaming. Fundamentally, the study suggests that for fashion SMEs looking to succeed in the online market, integrating live streaming into their marketing and sales tactics is not just advantageous, but necessary. By effectively utilizing live streaming's potential, along with fair pricing and robust social media marketing, fashion SMEs can significantly enhance customer involvement and impact their buying choices.

LIMITATION & FURTHER RESEARCH

This study, focusing on the Indonesian fashion industry as of 2023, presents findings that may not be widely applicable to other markets or industries, potentially limiting its broader relevance. The reliance on a relatively small sample size, primarily reflecting current consumer perceptions and behaviors towards live shopping platforms, may not encompass the diversity of broader consumer demographics. Additionally, the demographic diversity of the survey respondents might have influenced the outcomes, as a more varied participant pool could yield different results. Furthermore, the study's concentration on current trends without accounting for historical data or future projections narrows its scope, affecting the study's overall conclusions and applicability.

Future research has significant opportunities to expand upon this study. It could explore similar models in different cultural or geographical contexts, verifying the findings across various e-commerce platforms. Also, looking into live streaming's effects in non-fashion industries would offer a broader view of its efficiency. Longitudinal studies would be valuable in understanding the

evolving impact of live streaming on consumer choices and behaviors. Additionally, future studies should investigate how digital marketing strategies affect different consumer groups like millennials and Gen Z, particularly in terms of brand loyalty. The potential of new technologies, such as augmented reality, in enhancing live shopping experiences is another promising research area. This could provide deeper insights into new consumer engagement methods. Moreover, exploring the effectiveness of digital marketing in Indonesia's diverse cultural regions could yield insights into the nuances of region-specific marketing strategies.

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